

CHAPTER XVI

Public University: Extreme Capitalism and Branding. Assembling a Motley Puzzle

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1. INTRODUCTION

The social reality according to a holistic vision, said Samir Amine, is three-dimensional: economic, political, and cultural. (ريمس, s. d., p. 7) The relationship of the university to each of these dimensions is at least complex. The university contributes greatly to the creation of this social reality, and is retroactively affected by the changes it makes to it.

However, the economic dimension is the one that has had the greatest impact on the field of knowledge, and it has subsequently developed more advanced analytical tools than those used in the study of politics and culture. (پاسيم ريمس, s. d.)

Thus, this economic reality models societies by forcing them to conform to its parameters. However, it is within this logic that an extreme capitalism, subservient to the economist Milton Friedman, and its epiphenomena such as the consumer society and branding, tend to dominate the global economic climate. Naomi Klein, in this sense, says: "He -Milton Friedman- is credited with the credo of the contemporary globalized economy, characterized by hypermobility. (Klein *et al.*, 2010, p. 11)

For Milton Friedman, the essential function of government is « [...] de protéger notre liberté contre ses ennemis extérieurs et contre nos concitoyens eux-mêmes ; il fait régner la loi et l'ordre, il fait respecter les contrats privés, et il favorise la concurrence. » (Friedman & Fourçans, 2010, p. 41) The role of the state is therefore "... de fournir les policiers et les soldats, tout le reste, y compris l'éducation publique gratuite, n'est qu'ingérence au sein des marchés". (Klein *et al.*, 2010, p. 12)

Faced with the rise of this capitalist ideology, the Algerian public university is forced to adapt to an environment where competition is the key word. Competition between whom? With whom? This is where a brand image for the university, even a public one, is needed to give it an identity that sets it apart from competing parties.

2. BRANDING FOR THE PUBLIC UNIVERSITY, BUT WHICH ONE?

It is accepted that the capitalist model tends to spread geometrically, whether in the form of economic internationalisation, political globalisation or cultural standardisation. But it is also recognised that there is no one form of capitalism. “ Literature on varieties of capitalism (VoC) argues that capitalist economies can be classified into several types, which include liberal and coordinated market economies.” (Lee & Shin, 2021) However, what its various models have in common is the consecration of individual ownership of the means of production, which needs an identity to survive.

This identity, which has the characteristics of a brand image, acquires an importance under neo-liberalism that goes beyond the very product it designates. In the mid-1980s, a theory was developed to the effect that « ... pour réussir, les entreprises doivent d’abord fabriquer des marques, pas des produits. » (Klein *et al.*, 2017, p. 26)

The Algerian public university, as a producer of knowledge in the wake of extreme capitalism (neo-liberalism), is forced to work on its ‘Brand’. Although in this line of thought, this ‘Brand’ evokes a climate of competition that forces us to approach the university in the plural. Universities that work to market their products. In this case, knowledge.

This situation means that the university « ... affronte des défis de trois types. Le premier renvoie à une crise d’hégémonie entre ses fonctions traditionnelles et des fonctions nouvelles qui ont été progressivement introduites. Le deuxième renvoie à une crise de légitimité entre la hiérarchisation des savoirs spécialisés à travers la réduction de l’accès et l’exigence sociale de la politique de démocratisation des études universitaires. Le troisième renvoie à une crise institutionnelle résultant de la tension entre l’autonomie revendiquée par les universités et leur soumission à des critères d’efficacité et de productivité entrepreneuriale. » (Akkari & Santiago, 2017) Thus, the image of the public university in the face of this situation, which is described as « période de crise » (Akkari & Santiago, 2017) is a ‘Brand’ that is required to be financed for publicity, and which is frustrated by its status as an official name granted by the public authorities. As a corollary, the public university works to implement instructions from the political stratum, instead of producing (knowledge) according to a set of specifications.

3. START AT THE BEGINNING; INTERNAL BRANDING

Semiotically, a brand image is a mental, and therefore ideal, representation. One has even gone so far as to define the brand image in higher education as : « [...] a construct that allows its owners to augment the institution and its products using certain values. » (Chapleo & Clark, 2016) For Balmer « la mission et la philosophie » of the institution, is one of the key concepts for understanding its brand management. (Balmer, 1995) Now, an idea or a concept spreads from the inside (of a person or a society) to the outside. (Gustave Gabriel, 1993, p. 225) There is even an academic consensus that marketing

starts from the inside out. (Chapleo & Clark, 2016) Thus, branding a university starts with the employees' adherence to the idea of the brand itself before it is represented by the buyers, the student-customers.

This "internal branding" denotes: "the activities undertaken by an organization to ensure that the brand promise reflecting the espoused brand values that set customers expectations is enacted and delivered by employees." (Punjaisri & Wilson, 2011)

To this end, global universities are setting up rebranding committees to improve their brand analysis and decision making. (Chapleo & Clark, 2016) The contribution of the university's employees to its branding is crucial. (Sujchaphong *et al.*, 2015)

However, the employees of the Algerian public university, as civil servants, are subject to regulations that restrict their room for manoeuvre both in terms of regulations and economics. This situation is unsuited to the context of capitalism in the contemporary world.

Consequently, the recourse of the Algerian public university to advertising agencies, and the installation of internal rebranding committees, seems to present a possible solution, but one that would generate resistance on the part of the university's employees, who see the idea of branding as being contrary to their culture (tradition) formed in the past. Cahapleo Chris and Clark Paul point out this difficulty when they say « Embedded cultural resistance to branding is often an issue for universities. » (Chapleo & Clark, 2016)

3.1. Official name and simplicity of the symbol

If internal branding is a start by integrating all stakeholders. Externally it starts with the design of an intrinsically powerful brand. The status of an official name in the form of a national personality or a Wilaya (also national) seems to be a hindrance in the process of branding.

It is common for us to hesitate about how to write the names of our universities when they are proper names -which are written as they are meant to be- as is the case, for example, of the University of Algiers 2, Abou El Kacem Saad Allah. Moreover, a designation in the form of a wilaya name would raise a difficulty in its translation-reporting as a toponym. London (England) is the translation (correspondence) of "London" United Kingdom, but not of London from Ontario in Canada. (Delisle & Fiola, 2013) Algiers is the capital of Algeria, but also the name of Algiers Island in the Franz Josef Archipelago in Russia, and of Algiers County in Michigan, USA.

Advertising such a Brand would not be easy for the agencies or committees mentioned above, as it may denote other entities, and subsequently not give a stable identity to the university. This is in addition to their morphological complexity. It should be recalled here that the pioneers of the new branding model (Nike, Apple...) seek to « [...] trouver d'abord une idée abstraite ou une (image de) marque qui personnifie l'entreprise. S'en servir pour entrer en contact avec les consommateurs qui partagent ces valeurs. » (Klein *et al.*, 2017, p. 27)

Furthermore, the simplification of symbols accompanying brand images is an element of effectiveness, appeal and even strength. The example of Serge Tachakhotin's ranking of the best-known graphic symbols in order of increasing complexity, to support the thesis of superiority residing in the simplicity of symbols, is revealing. (Cachotin, 1992, p. 268)

In higher education worldwide, the phenomenon of rebranding has not been left behind. Several institutions in this field have resorted to rebranding in order to gain recognition for their identities. Examples include : Rose-Hulman Institute of Technology in the United States of America, whose naming history is used as a model for the effectiveness of rebranding in the university context (Petroski, 2019), and McDaniel College, Arcadia University and Stevenson University, which have implemented a radical *renaming* process. (Williams *et al.*, 2013)

This situation suggests that the Algerian university is resorting to a rebranding process that is supposed to (re)give it an identity brand as part of its internationalisation process.

4. CONCLUSION

The state, faced with the democratisation of access to higher education, is obliged to finance other activities of the university, or of the universities that depend on it, equitably and wrongly. In addition, this funding raises the question of the university's autonomy from public and political authorities.

The private sector could, insofar as a competitive economic climate is concerned, contribute by funding higher education, but not without a *quid pro quo*. Its funding would therefore be directed mainly towards the work of research laboratories, from which it would expect tangible and lucrative results.

Between the state and private sectors, the intermediate position is occupied by the "Economic Public Enterprises" and the "Public Establishments of an Industrial and Commercial Nature". This sector, which is supposed to represent a transitional stage towards the privatisation of public enterprises, and where the enterprises belonging to it enjoy financial autonomy, could be, albeit temporarily, an effective actor in the process of branding the university, through actions of sponsorship, funding of research work, and partnerships in general. Although the integration of 'EPICs' and 'EPEs' into the branding process of universities seems feasible, the same cannot be said for internal branding, for which the adoption of a system of subcontracting in administrative management does not seem to be imminent for the Algerian public university.

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